

SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF ABU NASR FARABI AND HIS CLASSIFICATION OF SCIENCES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7899707>

Abstract. This article talks about the life and work of Abu Nasr Farabi, the great thinker of the East, his scientific heritage, and socio-philosophical and epistemological ideas. In addition, the classification of sciences created by Farabi and its influence on the development of sciences are analyzed.

Key words. Abu Nasr Farabi, Plato, Aristotle, Baghdad, philosophy, logic, theology, ethics, politics, astronomy, chemistry, music, "Ikhwan al-Safa", classification of sciences.

Abu Nasr Farabi was born in the city of O'tror (a city located in Shymkent region of present-day Kazakhstan) in 256-257 Hijri. His father was a military officer. Young and sharp-witted, Abu Nasr Farabi was interested in science early, mastered Arabic and Persian languages perfectly. Farabi studied Sanskrit (an ancient Indian language) and was fluent in it. Belonging to the Turkic peoples, he knew his mother tongue well and mastered various languages and sciences at a young age. He lived mostly in Baghdad. That's why he knew Arabic and Greek well.

Farabi was an intellectual scholar who mastered various sciences well. He wrote dozens of books on philosophy, logic, theology, ethics, politics, astronomy, chemistry, music and other sciences. He was more interested in philosophy, logic and religious sciences.

Farabi's book on music is the most important Arabic book written in Islamic culture and is still one of the main sources. He invented a musical instrument called "Law". Abu Nasr Farabi died in 336 AH in one of the villages near Damascus. According to some sources, the total scientific legacy of Abu Nasr Farabi is more than 260. Some of them are:

"Risela fi Aza il Inson";

"Treatise on Aza al-Hayvan";

"Risola fi Raddi ala Jolinus fima Nakaza fiha Aristotelis";

"Kitabun fi Aroi ahl il-Madinatil Fazila";

"Risola fil Millatil-fazil";
"Taliqat";
"Risola fi Tahsil is Saodat";
"Risola uyun ul-Masail";
"Risala al-Mufarraqat";
"Treatise on the mind" and so on.

The books of Farabi are divided into two types. The first is the books written in education, philosophy and other fields. The second is the commentaries on the books of Plato, Aristotle and those who followed them. Some researchers say that the number of these books reached forty pieces.

Farabi tried hard to coordinate between Plato and Aristotle and Greek philosophy and Islam in his educational activities. He himself was a staunch Muslim. At the same time, he is the first Muslim philosopher who founded a philosophical school similar to that of Plato and Aristotle.

Once upon a time, Plato's book "al-Tosu'ot" was translated and mistakenly considered to be Aristotle's book. Farabi, who read this book known as "Rububiyat" in Arabic, was happy to find a document and proof that Aristotle's thoughts were similar to Plato's and tried to coordinate other books of these two philosophers. Farabi loved and appreciated both Plato and Aristotle equally.

At the same time, he could not imagine that the opinions of these two people would contradict each other. His book called "Al-Jam'u bayna ra'yay al-hakimayni Aflotun al-Ilohi va Arastutolis" - a compilation of the thoughts of the two judges - Ilohi Plato and Aristotle, is considered the culmination of Farabi's work in this regard.

Farabi divides knowledge into practical (vocation) and theoretical (science). In the framework of theoretical knowledge, the main place is occupied by philosophy, which Farabi describes as the science of the general characteristics and laws of existence, and defines its relation to certain sciences as the relation of the general to the particular.

Farabi was the first to create a classification of sciences in the Middle Ages, which was considered an encyclopedia of scientific knowledge at that time. Farabi divides all subjects into five groups:

1. The science of language consisting of seven sections;
2. Logic;
3. Mathematics, which is divided into seven independent subjects, namely, arithmetic, geometry, optics, science of the stars, science of music, science of

weights, and mechanics;
4. Natural and divine sciences, or metaphysics;
5. The science of city management (or political science), jurisprudence and speech.

In his classification of sciences, Farabi takes into account the uniqueness of what each science studies, the nature of its laws, and the means of knowledge specific to them. In the Farabi system, the rule about philosophy "science of sciences" is expressed. According to Farabi, science and all knowledge in general do not arise from subjective desire and desire, but rather as a result of human needs that grow more and more in relation to them. Farabi's classification of sciences had a strong influence on the classification of sciences in the East and in Europe, and played an important role in their development.

The system created by Farabi is universal in content and covers all the important issues of the sciences of his time:

- general problems of philosophy;
- natural science issues;
- main philosophical knowing existence;
- controversial problems of logic;
- close connection between man and nature;
- including environmental issues.

Farabi's socio-philosophical thoughts have a humanistic character with their comprehensiveness, depth and meaning. In his work "The City of Virtuous People", which is considered to be the masterpiece of Farabi's literary heritage, he further clarified the idea put forward by Aristotle, who defined man as a social phenomenon first of all, and wrote the following: human needs many things in order to live and reach oily level of maturity, which he cannot acquire by himself, and to them.

"Each man is so constituted by his nature that he needs many things in order to live and to reach maturity at the family level, which he cannot obtain by himself, and in order to obtain them, human beings need for a community... the activities of the members of such a community as a whole supply each of them with what is necessary for their survival and maturity. Therefore, human individuals multiply and settle on the inhabited part of the earth, resulting in the human community is created."

If we pay attention, this idea is based on the controversial issue which is the main problem of philosophy - the emergence, formation and maturity of a

person. The most important thing in this process is a clear and concise opinion about the role and importance of the community. In fact, Farabi is a great scientist who is far ahead of his time with his worldview, a fighter of science and enlightenment, a great person who strives to reveal the laws of nature and social development. In his works:

- a perfect person;
- virtuous citizen;
- righteous ruler;
- happiness, ways to achieve it;
- characteristics of the state;
- moral and intellectual education;
- advanced ideas about the social perspective.

Refuting the philosophy of Farabi what is impossible is that he recognized theoretical philosophy as a real and basic science, and put all other sciences in the status of secondary fields subordinate to him. Not content with common worldviews between philosophies, but with religion put in the position. Not satisfied with the common worldviews between philosophies, he also placed religion and philosophy in separate parts. In his opinion, the proofs of the problems in philosophy were explained by the prophets in the form of symbols, therefore, in terms of essence, there is no difference between philosophy and religion. Such a view was finally successful in its time and became a way of thinking that defines the basis and method of Islamic philosophy.

Farabi's teachings played an important role in the further development of socio-philosophical thoughts in the East and Europe. He greatly influenced the views of the members of the Ikhwan as-Safa ("Pure Brothers"), a philosophical group from Basra, and the views of Abu Sulayman Mantiqi, Ibn Miskawayh, Ibn Bajja, Ibn Tufail, and Maimonides. The great scientist Ibn Sina considered him his teacher.

In conclusion, it can be said that one of the prominent representatives of the world science and culture, the renaissance era, Farabi highly appreciated the place of ancient Greek science and culture in human civilization and relied not only on it throughout his scientific career, but was endlessly amazed and inspired. He promoted the works of Greek scientists, especially Aristotle, who left an indelible mark on human history, and translated many of them into Arabic. Abu Nasr Farabi, who understood well that it is impossible to develop science and culture without fully studying the legacy left by the scientists of the ancient world, did not blindly follow the ideas of Greek thinkers, but he himself

was the successor of versatile scientists and creators, he showed himself as an independent thinker in the conditions of his time.

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